

Once-weekly semaglutide in adolescents with obesity.

Article summary

In this trial were examined about 201 participants at age from 12 to 18 with obesity or overweight. The study group was divided into two parts. The first group received semaglutide in a 2.4 mg weekly dose, while the rest of the patients received placebo. BMI (Body Mass Index) among the respondents was hesitated between 85th and 95th percentile. 90% of participants completed the treatment. In addition to pharmacological treatment, participants have to change their lifestyle. Criteria of exclusions were having a bariatry surgery, obesity treatment within 90days, uncontrolled metabolism diseases and psychiatric disorders such as bulimia, nervosa or suicide attempt. All of the participantst were examined at baseline(table 1) and after 68 weeks(table 2) of the trial.Study showed that in the group of adolescents in both group placebo and semaglutide, with changes in lifestyle in both, resulted clinically relevant decreases in BMI.

Table 1.

Shows characteristics of the participants at basedline like: Sex, Age, race, levels of biochemical indicators relevant to the study. It shows differences between the experimental group and the placebo group. It is a reference to information about the basic parameters of the examined people. From the table it can be inferred that men dominate in terms of gender, while the vast majority of respondents are white in terms of race. The baseline weight significant in this study in the semaglutide group was on average 109.9 kg while in placebo group it was 102,6kg. The average of the height was in the semaglutyd group 170,1 cm while in the placebo it was 169,7cm. Another quite important factor included in the study was the survey of young people using a IWQOL questionnaire to assess the level of life satisfaction which at the baseline was on average 84,0 score.

Table 2.

This table shows the final results of the study at week 68, which shows that there was a 16% decrease in BMI in the semaglutide group and a 0.8% decrease in the placebo group. The mean weight reduction in the semaglutide group was 15.3 kg, compared to 2.7 kg in the placebo group. Among the semaglutide group, there was a marked difference from the level of quality of life before and after the study, as well as an overall decrease in systolic and diastolic blood pressure levels, a decrease in percentage in lipid levels.

Table 3.

Presents side effects/ adverse events associated with taking semaglutide. As predicted in the semaglutide group, the most common adverse events were gastrointestinal problems such as nausea, vomiting, and less often diarrhea but they still posed problems in a small percentage of the subjects, while in the placebo group these events occurred in an even smaller percentage.

Figure A.

The figure shows the percentage of change in BMI in relation to the duration of the study (in weeks) in the two study groups, it shows that in the placebo group the BMI level did not decrease significantly, while in the group using semaglutide it decreased significantly. The largest decrease was recorded between weeks 35 and 68 of the study. This shows that you have to wait patiently for the effects of drug therapy.

Figure B.

This figure informs about number of participants that loose their weight during the procedure. The graph shows how many percent of study participants in each group, placebo and semaglutide, lost about 5%, 10%, 15% and 20% of their weight relative to their baseline weight. Referring to the graph, it can be concluded that the semaglutide group showed a much higher percentage of people who lost weight compared to the placebo group. In some cases, it is ten times larger.

Figure C.

Shows the change in BMI in the semaglutide group at week 68 of the study duration. It follows that the largest reduction in BMI (>20%) occurred in 40% of the subjects. In addition, Figure C. informs that in 76% of the subjects the reduction in BMI was at least at the level of 5%.

Figure D.

Shows the change BMI in the placebo group at week 68 of the study. It informs that a reduction in BMI levels above 20% occurred in only 3% of the surveyed people. On the other hand, a 5% decrease in BMI levels was experienced by 23% of the respondents.

Figure E.

This figure shows BMI according to weeks since randomization. It provides information on both groups. In people using semaglutide, BMI levels steadily decreased until week 44 of the study. In contrast, in the placebo group, BMI levels didn't decrease or increase significantly.

Figure F.

The figure shows the change in body weight (in kilograms) in relation to the week of randomization in both study groups. It shows that among people using semaglutide, body weight began to decrease steadily, the largest decrease occurred between 16 and 44 weeks of the study and amounted to about 10 kg. In the placebo group body weight remained on average more or less at the same level.

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Journal

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